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SOME OF WHAT IT IS THAT DONALD JUDD COMES TO FIND OUT WITH RESPECT TO SPACE

We even have a feeling about a rock, about anything.

—“Yale Lecture,” 1983¹

What is in front of you is what exists, what is given. This fundamental rock in the road is what must be described and analyzed. The rock is a philosophical problem and a structure must be built to deal with it and beyond that a philosophical structure must be built to deal with the fact that there is more than one rock, even a lot.

—“A Long Discussion Not About Master-pieces but Why There Are So Few of Them, Part II,” 1984²

Bones on the land. Bones and rocks.

—Interview with Joshua Homnick and Rainer Judd, 1993³

HIGH TIME

Mrs. May Tupper Quick’s eighth-grade history class sets out on a field-trip across town, down North Austin Street, a right at West El Paso there just past the tracks, and on along to Donald Judd’s property by the Godbold feed-mill. It’s around 1978, November maybe, in Marfa, Texas. A ways into the students’ interview with the famous New York artist and only-recent full-time resident here, one young lady haltingly recites her question. “H-have you, nnh, uh, have you reached y-your main goal in life or are you still pursuing it?”⁴ She must be about age fourteen, no doubt already wearying of grown-ups’ say-so, but maybe a bit too young to pick up on how lonesome and despairing most of them truly are. Judd lets loose a single gentle chuckle. Five months back he himself turns fifty—which folks call mid-life even though as a rule you’re long past that. If he answers her *yes I’ve reached my main goal in life*, then what’s he to do from here on out, and if it’s *no I’m still pursuing it*, really oughtn’t he re-consider the chances of ever seeing through what he hopes to. Judd’s reply comes curiously ready, as if now and again these same concerns toss around in his own head. “That goal keeps changing for everybody,” he tells her. “I’ve certainly, done what I, wanted to do in the very beginning, but then you think of more things to do. So, you don’t catch up. But I think I’ve gotten a lot more work done than I ever expected to do.”

To me that sounds like the quiet pride of a man who’s achieved something in his life and knows it, a man who also has a mind to take on plenty more before he’s through. But then have a look at scattered lines from an article he writes only fifteen years later, when he’s unwell and about to get the hard news of his cancer that November of ’93 (another three months after which, he passes).⁵

Since now it is common for work to be placed anywhere in a room, it is impossible for people to understand that placement on the floor and the absence of a pedestal were inventions. I invented them. [...] Nothing had ever been placed directly on the floor.

A new idea is quickly debased, often before the originator has time and money to continue it. In general I think this has happened to all of my work, but especially to the use of the whole room, which is now called an installation, which basically I began. [...] A direct relationship to the supporting structure had not existed before.

I think that I developed space as a main aspect of art. [...] My work on the floor was a new form, creating space amply and strongly.

The three-dimensional work that I began in 1962 was new and the complete use of color was new. [...] Color and three-dimensional space were placed directly on the floor, as one. Neither existed before.

If the list of exhibitions at the back of the catalogues is related to what the exhibitions contained, the diversity is obvious and the substantial prior invention proven.⁶

It’s a tough read, make no mistake: sitting and watching as an artist tries to prove his success to you. Beneath the fist-pounding declarations of discovery and the barbed frustration at others’ misuse or neglect, I believe you can hear the voice of a dying man who doesn’t want to die. Judd’s not ready to let go, and isn’t planning on doing so peaceably.

For the record, though, he also includes remarks in this same text which soften and complicate the heavy-handed pronouncements that he’s the one who comes up with an assortment of major ideas you find all throughout art today. “Placement on the floor and the absence of a pedestal were inventions. I invented them,” and yet, “I think there was a small flat work on the floor by Lucas Samaras done at the same time or earlier”⁷ “The use of the whole room, which is now called an installation, ... basically I began,” although “in 1923 Lissitzky built the *Proun Raum* and in the late twenties Schwitters built the *Merzbau*.”⁸ Lastly, “I developed space as a main aspect of art,” however “I was not completely alone[.]”⁹ There was Lee Bontecou, John Chamberlain, “the canvas works by Oldenburg, enclosing a soft space, a flexible space, and the glass works by Larry Bell, which contained a visible space The other artist who has thoroughly developed space is of course Richard Serra.”

The seeming contradiction here—*I invented blank, and so did others at the same time or ahead of me*—illustrates Judd’s complaint about how there’s “no history” of space in art which he can refer to, something that’s part of the larger problem of wide-spread inattention to exactly what artist makes exactly what discoveries.¹⁰ “The earlier knowledge isn’t regarded as knowledge, but as appearance, as style, and so cannot continue, cannot accumulate, as scientific knowledge does.... One of the many destructive assumptions now is that all ideas have no originators. ... But someone

invents ideas. Someone wants something new.”¹¹ I suppose it might be possible that in those lines from before Judd’s simply trying to show us how the lack of an accepted history of space in art leads him to unknowingly re-invent the already-existing notions of placement on the floor, absence of the pedestal, use of the whole room, and space as a main aspect. Then again, he does sound as if he’s insisting that he himself works on these ideas earlier and more fully than anybody else. My guess is that at first Judd claims he invents this and that as he goes along writing; on re-considering, though, he sees how debatable such statements are; all the same he decides to keep them in, but also to add some hedging sentences about other artists; and in the end he just ignores the inconsistencies that those then bring about. He’s short on time, don’t forget.

Not to mention he still has a fair amount to set straight. For one thing, Judd’s been making his art for thirty-odd years and even now only a very few really get anything out of viewing it.¹² And someday soon he’ll need to leave the objects behind to the rest of the civilization. (He uses that word *civilization* ten times in his article; the thinking is big, and the writing plain and unreserved. Why hold back at this late hour.¹³) The problem, so far at least, is that people tend to treat the work pretty badly. A hot-shot art-collector by the name of Giuseppe Panza has shoddy knock-offs built at will; a Charles Saatchi buys a work then won’t let Judd oversee its installation; the museum in Pasadena, California, puts up a show and the seventy-two-page booklet has sixty-four errors.¹⁴ The art-critics and art-historians are hopeless, as usual.¹⁵ And, worst of all, Judd believes fellow artists are squandering the knowledge of color and space you can take away from his objects (he names Barbara Kruger).¹⁶ So you understand where it’s coming from, this furious last-ditch attempt by Judd to catch us up on everything he learns in his life. *Look at the works and the space for chrissakes*, he about shouts from the page. *There they are. Look at them and think about them.* It may be the man’s searing final wish, and what comes to replace the easy-going assuredness in his talk with the local school-kids not so very long before.

THE SPACE AROUND AN APPLE CORE ...

“Over two hundred years ago Samuel Johnson kicked a rock to prove its existence; fifty years ago Wallace Stevens described the effect of a jar upon the wilderness; this year there are two rocks; obviously this leisurely pace is too fast.”¹⁷ Too fast, Judd means, for a civilization as “gross” as he finds ours in the “inglorious present.”¹⁸ Already you see how what he has to tell will chafe some, and, yes, he might’ve taken a more kindly and patient tone. But so be it: he reckons that when it comes to space, the whole lot of us know nothing or thereabouts.

There is no vocabulary for a discussion of space in art. There was a traditional vocabulary about space in architecture, about proportion, volume and sequence, East and West, but it was discredited in the seventies by the architects who are not architects, and so could not judge. They appropriated the appearance without knowing the substance. For both art and architecture, the vocabulary of space of the past should be reconsidered and in relation, but newly, which is not impossible, a vocabulary should be built.¹⁹

At the present space and color have in common complete neglect. [...] There has been almost no discussion of space in art, nor in the present. The most important and developed aspect of present art is unknown. This concern, my main concern, has no history. There is no context; there are no terms; there are not any theories. There is only the visible work invisible.²⁰

And time is wasting. (“It’s a short life and a little speed is necessary,” Judd remarks in 1983, age fifty-five. Next, in ’87, “the long extent of time compared to life, which is very short, is quite obvious.” In ’89, “I have a short life” and “it’s not news that life is short.” In ’92, “is life big or little? It’s short.” Then in that text from ’93, “the new work seemed to be the beginning of my own freedom, with possibilities for a lifetime. The possibilities and the lifetime are now well along.”²¹) Perhaps on account of

Fig. 1:
Lucas Samaras, *Untitled (Floor Piece)*
1961. Sculp-Metal on wood. Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York.
Gift of the artist, 2014.

these reasons Judd figures we sorely need some lessons and basic exercises, a primer of sorts to get ourselves ready to view his art and the space it makes, all of which is to say, something written down that’ll be helpful to us if we’re to set about trying to get a sense of the man’s thinking on the topic of space a quarter-century or more after he’s gone.

“Space is so unknown,” Judd starts off, “that a discussion of it would have to begin with a rock.”²² (“I’m not describing how a primitive discussion of space began thousands of years ago, but how a primitive discussion might begin tomorrow, if this civilization were advanced enough to bear it.”) It’s best if you’re willing to take a moment and pick out a real rock because using your mind’s eye to picture one isn’t the same. Judd has questions for us.

1. How large is it?
2. Is it on a level surface?
3. Does it rest on the surface or does it perch?
4. Is the rock symmetrical?
5. If not, does it face away or toward the tilted surface?
6. Is the top of the rock pointed, rounded, flat but symmetrical with the sides, flat but broader than the sides ... ?
7. Then, what if a second rock is placed nearby?
8. How far apart are the two rocks?
9. Is one larger than the other?
10. Do the rocks have the same shape or is one pointed and the other round?
11. If they are on a slope, which is higher, which joins the plane as an entity?²³

After putting the first half-dozen of these to us, Judd sums up the wider notion he’d have us turn our thoughts to. “In general, in what way does the rock create space around itself? It is a definition of space, a center of space, in one way a core of space.”²⁴

I don’t have to tell you, that’s a fairly odd thing to say about a rock. Yet the words *definition* and *center* and *core* make it sound a lot like how Judd understands “Giacometti’s standing figures, which are the apple core of their spatial apple, and then Newman’s related vertical sculpture, and, also linear, Olle Baertling’s sculpture”^{figs. 2-4}.²⁵ (He also writes thirty years before that Giacometti’s “polelike figures are the core of the space surrounding them; the empty space appears to push inward on the figures, compressing them into an obdurate shaft.... The core defining its space is a paramount idea.”²⁶)

For Judd this apple of defined space is different from what’s alongside “all earlier sculptures.”²⁷ As examples of things within that sizeable category he names the boulders in Scotland with pre-historic cup markings, Michelangelo’s *David*, and the wood statues in Japanese

temples^{figs. 5, 6}. Such works are “monolithic,” “totemic,” akin to “the stone in the field,” Judd claims, and in each case the space you get is “negative” and “pictorial” since it’s nothing but the background and surrounds in which the positive object exists.²⁸ “The articulation of the solids ... is always much more important than the articulation of the resulting spaces. The space around the work is only somewhere from which to look toward the continuous solids.” In that final text of Judd’s you find a change, however. There he has us staring at an actual stone in a field, and he allows for the possibility that instead of just sitting in negative and pictorial space, the rock will create space around itself by becoming a definition or center or core of space like the objects by Giacometti, Newman, and Baertling.

To be clear, we’re talking here about an uncommonly specialized use of the every-day word *space*—no longer meaning simply *area, room, expanse*, and so forth, but rather what you wind up with when order and definition get introduced into those kinds of un-ordered and under-defined intervals. “You see, I am interested in space and in what defines the space, what is visible,” Judd explains.²⁹ Because “there is no space, in itself, as a ‘something’ that continues throughout everywhere ... like ether.”³⁰ Instead what happens is, “a given thing creates an interesting space.”³¹ “When you make a work of art, you are making space,” which is to say that “by making lines or points or planes in space, you actually make the space.”³² Still, creating or positioning an object is only part of it. Judd believes making space comes down to something else—us. “People make space,” he declares.³³ “Space [is] just the way we feel about it,” “it is made by thought.”³⁴

But, hold on, does the art make the space, or do we make the space by thought? Well, the two manners of describing the situation seem to amount to the same thing for Judd. If you and I can agree that on looking

Fig. 2:
Alberto Giacometti, *Figurine*
1961. Bronze. Fondation Giacometti, Paris.

Fig. 3:
Barnett Newman, *Broken Obelisk*
1963-67. Cor-ten steel. Rothko Chapel, Houston, Texas.

Fig. 4:
Olle Baertling, *Yzib*
1969. Saltsjöbaden, Sweden.

at a broad- and flat-topped rock we’ll be likely to think of and thereby create a broad flat space around it, then after a while, once we grow a bit more accustomed to the whole idea, we might begin to look on the rock itself as creating this space. It’s a quick short-hand due to Judd’s hurrying, I’ll wager. The problem, though, is how this looser way of putting it—that it’s the rock or the art that makes the space—sure comes close to mixing up physical reality with the thoughts and the feelings we have toward it. In other instances Judd pays careful attention to the issue. “Obviously what you feel and what things are aren’t the same,” he states, compared to “the old confusion of nature being what it is felt to be.”³⁵ He has more to add on the subject when viewing an ice-cream cone by Claes Oldenburg, some marbles and bronzes by Jean Arp, and the desert in West Texas^{figs. 7-9}.

Strictly speaking, Judd argues, “the desirable ice cream cone is the cone desired,” in other words, desired by him or by Oldenburg or by you or by me, but wrong to see as being desirable by nature, or in its essence desirable, since “it is very elementary philosophy that objects do not have essences.”³⁶ “This is what’s interesting about Oldenburg,” he goes on.³⁷ “He’s not saying anything about, say, the ice-cream cone, so much. He’s saying, it’s clear that he’s saying, I feel, he, Claes, feels this about the ice-cream cone. He’s not saying inside that ice-cream cone there’s some essence, some real philosophical matter, because we can’t, ah, scientifically and philosophically and in all considerations, we can’t believe that now.” Judd also likes the sculptures by Arp with no more than an “oblique reference” to the human body as opposed to an unmistakable “resembl[ance],” “approximation,” or “description” of the body that’ll of

Fig. 5:
Nether Largie Standing Stones
Kilmartin, Argyll and Bute, Scotland.

course always be chock-full of meaning.³⁸ About the not-full ones Judd writes, “the emptiness suggests that if you are interested in a thing it is interesting, and if you are not it is not. That isn’t as obvious as it sounds.” And with respect to the desert, “most people think, looking out, that what they feel about the landscape, it feels. But it isn’t theirs.”³⁹

Last September [1985 or '86, Judd is fifty-seven or -eight] ... the desert was spare, as usual, but very green and beautiful. I realized that the land and presumably the rabbits, quail, lizards and bugs didn’t know that this was beautiful. Only I knew it, or we, since such observations are assumed to be held in common by everyone, all of us being perceptive at a distance. But then I realized that the observation is only ours, the same as the lizard’s opinion of the bug. The observation has no relevance, no validity, no objectivity, and so the land was not beautiful—who’s to say? It simply exists. My saying that it’s beautiful is as pointless beyond myself as saying, following Berkeley, that what I see cannot exist without me. Thinking the land beautiful is large and natural and I or anyone assumes everything agrees. Or to start over, it becomes somewhat lonesome when I realize that only we appreciate it, although there is still the communal assumption and some small hope of objectivity. But when I realize that our appreciation is really only mine or anyone’s, with nothing wider, that the appreciation exists as everything does, that’s it. There is no meaning. Except that it exists.⁴⁰

Fig. 7:
Claes Oldenburg, *Floor Cone*
1962. Synthetic polymer paint on canvas filled with foam rubber and cardboard boxes.
Museum of Modern Art, New York. Gift of Philip Johnson.

Fig. 6:
Torso of Standing Buddha
Jogan Period, 9th century. Wood. Toshodaiji, Nara, Japan.

Fig. 8:
Jean (Hans) Arp, *Growth (Croissance)*
1938. Marble. The Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum.

Or, as Judd claims elsewhere, “the only reality that can be known at once and more or less completely is oneself.”⁴¹ So we might casually remark on how an ice-cream cone is desirable, how Arp’s sculptures are interesting, how the desert is beautiful, and how something makes space. But all we can ever truly mean by this is that we think and feel the ice-cream cone to be desirable, Arp’s sculptures to be interesting, the desert to be beautiful, and rocks and art-works to be capable of making space. One more thing: Judd has it that “any work of art, old or new, is harmed or helped by where it is placed [and] this can almost be considered objectively, that is, spatially.”⁴² At the end of the sentence there he sort of implies that space is objective (or almost objective), however, as with the beauty of the desert, I believe you have to allow that in fact it’s nothing more than one’s own assumption of common agreement and one’s own small hope of objectivity.

By way of continuing to explain about space Judd tells of how as a student he “realized that the space underneath the desk was a lot more interesting than what was happening down in the art school. It always looked very good under there.”⁴³ Sure enough, the top and legs of a desk mark out the void below and between, which then can become interesting and

Fig. 9:
Las Casas, Ayala de Chinati ranch
Presidio County, Texas.

start looking good to somebody who sees it as a space. But without anyone for it to seem interesting to, look good to, appear as space to—and with that, turn into space for—it'll stay plain old emptiness. And this Judd calls *undefined* or *indefinite* space, “weak, nondescript, neutral space,” barely or not even space at all in some ways because as yet unseen and un-thought-about.⁴⁴ In other words, space is something you think up and feel based on what else is there. It's as real as any thought and feeling is, but it isn't a physical fact like volume, and it can't be shown to be “true scientifically.”⁴⁵

The apple Judd mentions is one kind of space, that which forms around an object, like, say, a work of art. Chances are you'll view the space as being at its clearest and most defined near the core, then steadily less so farther off, and at a given distance as petering out altogether (in this sense unlike an actual apple, it must be said, seeing as how an actual apple is fully apple until it stops dead at its peel; though no great surprise that the analogy doesn't fit perfectly). Judd describes the way his smaller works “make space around them ... which just trails off.”⁴⁶ “If you take a free-standing piece, it controls a certain amount of space, but that space, at a certain distance from the piece, goes off into whatever the rest of the room is.”⁴⁷ And again, “the space generated by the object just sort of trail[s] off in four directions. [...] Spatially it trails off in all directions into ah indefinite space.”⁴⁸ His works out in the land do this too^{fig. 10}. “The small pieces can be put up right here [indoors] and I hope that they're very three-dimensional, therefore they make space around them that has no borders, it just trails off. For the big concrete pieces in Texas in the field, if you take the whole piece and then you go away from it, about the same sort of thing happens.”⁴⁹ How space is *made*, how it's *generated*, how it *trails off*, how it's *indefinite* when far and *definite* closer in—Judd's already well on his way to building a vocabulary, a philosophy even, so as to try and deal with the space his art makes.

I'm wondering if he might also hold that a relationship exists between the physical volume of a thing such as a rock (the apple core, you recall) and the non-physical, wholly thought and felt space that we come to see the rock as creating around itself (the apple meat). If you're willing to grant this for the time being at least, we'll be able to talk through a few of the shapes space can take, even if in the end it's always going to be invisible.

Perhaps space reaches from each side of our rock roughly the measure of the nearest corresponding dimension, be it length, width, or height: so about as long as the length of the rock to its left and to its right, the width of the rock in front and in back, and the height of the rock above (and below too if not for the ground, unless for you the space does indeed bore down into the earth a ways). The rock with the broad flat top lies in a long, wide, and low space, while a rock whose top is not as broad and flat might be in a shorter, narrower, and higher space. Or maybe the space stretches the length of a rock's longest dimension in every direction. Or we can view the space as sticking closely to the contours of a rock, bringing about a lumpy apple that follows its lumpy edges. Judd won't settle on any single possibility for us because it's we ourselves who have to do the thinking that makes the space. Plus, this is only one type. There're others you can think of and feel besides that which surrounds a thing.

... INSIDE A JAR ...

Early on Judd takes a liking to the several ways that Robert Morris's objects create space, for instance^{fig. 11}. “The *Cloud* occupies the space above and below it, an enormous column. The triangle fills a corner of the room, blocking it. The angle encloses the space within it, next to the wall. The occupancy of space, the access to or denial of it, is very specific.”⁵⁰ And the same out-spoken Marfa middle-schooler asks Judd later in the class visit about a work of his in the room^{fig. 12}. “That, that, um, sculpture right there. Um, can't you put it into a picture and paint it?”⁵¹ “Yeah, but why?” he answers. “It's all about three dimensions, and the space inside the boxes,

Fig. 10:
Donald Judd, 15 untitled works in concrete
1980–1984. Chinati Foundation, Marfa, Texas.

Fig. 11:
Robert Morris, installation view
December 16, 1964–January 9, 1965. Green Gallery, New York.

around the boxes, between the boxes. It's all about space, and you can't paint the space or anything, you can only make it exist. It's about seeing and about the actuality of space.” We know of the space around a thing by now, though not yet as much with regard to the space inside and between.

If Judd refers to an apple when he walks us through what surrounds an object, it's a glass and a jar when he speaks of what's within.

All old sculpture, great as it is, from any civilization, is monolithic; it is the stone that Dr. Johnson kicked at Harwich and not the glass that you pick up.... David Smith's work, for example, is the last of the stone in the field. It is the placement of Stevens's jar on a hill, fundamental, but the least developed articulation by a work of art. The jar itself, like the glass, is new.⁵²

Judd seems to be saying that a jar and a glass accomplish the basic task of making space around themselves sheerly as a result of being placed someplace—like a David Smith work does, like the Scottish boulder and *David* and Japanese Buddha all do, like our rock does. (A pretty “fundamental” kind of space, then, one which is not terribly “articulat[ed]”; although remember how objects by Giacometti and Newman and Baertling manage to create space circling their linear cores that has what Judd might call a more “developed” degree of articulation.)

Fig. 12:
Donald Judd, *To Susan Buckwalter*
1964. Galvanized iron and blue lacquer on aluminum. 30 x 141 x 30 inches.
Judd Foundation, Marfa, Texas.

Okay, but the jar and the glass also form a space on their insides. This is different. It's contained by the thing and as such very well-defined, while the space around the thing is uncontained and fairly ill-defined. What I mean is that you have one type of space which butts up against the inner sides of your jar and stops cold, but you're going to have a tougher time figuring out for certain where the other type of space surrounding the jar becomes entirely unrelated to it and therefore halts. Because when the space gets far enough removed that it no longer makes a great deal of sense to look at as being quote-unquote around the outside of the jar—at one foot away, say, or five, or twenty—right there it'll cease to be defined and instead become undefined or indefinite, back to being part of the emptiness elsewhere in the room.

"A lot of the pieces work with the internal space," Judd states. "It very much is a case of what's inside of it and what's outside of it."⁵³ "The works ... create internal as well as external space. [...] The smallest, simplest work creates space around it, since there is so much space within."⁵⁴ "One of my main concerns is to, um, develop the three-dimensionality as much as possible. And that's why the space inside is vital."⁵⁵ A good many of his objects, we're to understand, are like glasses and jars in that they make space not only around themselves but on their insides as well. Judd probably believes all of this is plain to see. It surely isn't for me.

Hearing some more from him on jar-like art will be helpful. With John Chamberlain's sculptures, "there is not space through the work; there is a lot in it."⁵⁶ Take *Miss Lucy Pink* of 1962^{fig. 13}. "The metal seems superfluous because its involutions enclose so much space; the form is not only metal but is also space. The metal surrounds space like the eggshell of a sucked egg, instead of defining it with a line, core or plane." I view the eggshell here as akin to the jar owing to how both make space by containing it.

What's more, Judd points out that several distinct varieties of space can be on the inside of an object. In a work of his from 1968, which he regards as a "tube" and a "box" and "one wall within another," "you get two different types of space—the compressed space formed by the two walls

Fig. 13:
John Chamberlain, *Miss Lucy Pink*
1962. Painted and chromium-plated steel.
Private collection.

Fig. 14:
Donald Judd, *untitled*
1968. Anodized aluminum. [Destroyed]

and the open tubular space"^{fig. 14}.⁵⁷ The space in the narrow gap between the inner and outer nested walls does appear awfully compressed, and the space in the middle of the work is a heck of a lot more open. (This, in spite of how a drinking glass and a jam jar strike me as being more or less regular shapes that create really only a single kind of space within themselves—another moment when Judd's analogy may come up short. An eggshell's better. And what about a run-of-the-mill plastic milk jug. There's quite a bit happening in one: changing widths and rates of tapering from the belly to shoulder to neck to mouth of the container, and then the handle which not only has space in it for the milk, but also, being a thing for your fingers to grab onto, space around and through it too.) You see how it gets to be more interesting to use your time going over the space

Fig. 15:
Donald Judd, *untitled*
1962. Cadmium red light oil on wood with black enameled iron pipe. 48 x 32 1/2 x 21 1/4 inches.
Judd Foundation, Marfa, Texas.

Fig. 15a:
Schematic illustration of Donald Judd, untitled, 1962.

on the inside, or insides, of an object rather than the less defined space in its surrounds. That type will be there too, but Judd doesn't much care to step us through it again in his discussion of the Chamberlain and his own double-walled work.

Another object of Judd's turns up in a good amount of the recent writing^{fig. 15. 58} It's red and black, wood and metal, and he places it along with other art-works in a large room in the west building at his place by the feed-mill. Here's how Judd himself describes it (and you'll have to forgive my add-ons to his words—I'm hoping to make things clearer instead of complicating them even further). "In 1962 I made a right angle of wood placed directly on the floor.... The size of the [red wooden] right angle is determined by the right angle of a black pipe, whose two open ends are the centers of the outer planes of the [wood] right angle, which is painted cadmium red light; red and black, and black as space."⁵⁹ More:

There is scarcely an inside and an outside, only the space within the [red] angle and the space beyond the [red] angle. The only enclosed space is inside the pipe [where water would go]. This slight linear space determines the dimensions of the broad [red] planes. The shell of this narrow space [that is, the pipe itself] passes through the breadth of the inner angle [formed by the red planes], a definite space through a general space.⁶⁰

The piped space looks definite to Judd and the space it cuts across looks *general*, a new term which must mean *less- or not-definite*. Elsewhere he says of his art-work that "some of it has, you know, sort of a vague relationship to the space, and some of it, and some of it's quite particular."⁶¹ And we hear how when it comes to space, "you can have different degrees. It can be very general or it can be very particular."⁶² *Defined, definite, and particular* on the one hand, and on the other, *undefined, indefinite, general*, and also *vague* (a word I take as characterizing not only the relationship of an

Figs. 15b, 15c:

Schematic illustrations of Donald Judd, untitled, 1962.

object to space but also by extension the space itself that results, which is what happens with his two uses of *particular* there). Why not follow Judd's lead and try and rank the assorted kinds of space in the right-angled work according to their degrees of this property.

Here goes. We might begin with the openness in the room where it's far enough away from the art that there's almost no relation to it, no order, no definition—barely space at all since barely thought of by anybody as being such^{fig. 15a}. It's the vague and general type Judd talks of before: negative and pictorial, no more than fundamental, largely unarticulated, and made (such as it is) even by old sculptures just by virtue of being placed somewhere, again, like the monolith and totem and stone in the field that due to this same very basic fact create the same very basic kind. A more particular and more definite space still lies "beyond the angle" yet tighter-in, like an apple around its core^{fig. 15b}. A third is "within the angle," contained by the red wooden sides as if in a glass or a jar (or maybe closer to a saucer or a plate with "scarcely an inside and an outside"). Judd calls this space "general," though if you ask me it's noticeably less general and more defined than the first couple types, the negative-pictorial and the apple. Also he skips over how this space within the object splits in two. There's the oddly-shaped column inside the red angle but outside of the black angle^{fig. 15c}, and then there's the standing shaft girdled by the black pipe and running up the corner where the red sides come together^{fig. 15d}. Last, number five is "inside the pipe," "enclosed" and "linear," "shelled" and "narrow," thoroughly well-defined^{fig. 15e}. I for one don't often pay attention to the five kinds of space or degrees of definition you have around, inside, between, and through a thing. But you and I and others are able to sit down and have a conversation on the topic all thanks to what Judd accomplishes here.⁶³

A final point before moving on. Judd uses the word *determine* twice as he goes about explaining this work, yet you'll note a big difference between the two instances. First he writes that "the size of the [red] right angle is determined by the right angle of a black pipe." Here he's either stating a physical fact about how he builds the object in '62, or he's only remarking on how it appears to be built. For the sake of argument, let's say he does start by finding or assembling the compound bend of pipe, and, after that, he joins together the wood boards to form the red planes.⁶⁴ In this case the L of pipe will indeed determine the exact width of both planes, given that each of the pipe ends has to be perfectly centered left-to-right in its own plane, and the two planes have to perfectly meet at a corner. (Put again: if one arm of the pipe L is longer or shorter, then the red plane parallel to this arm has to be proportionally wider or narrower. You see, that's the only way you can keep both planes touching at the corner while also keeping the end of the other arm centered left-to-right in its plane. I'm using a model on my table to figure this out; you might want to try it if you have a minute.) And contrariwise too. If Judd in fact begins with the red planes and they happen to be wider or narrower than they are, he'll need to proportionally lengthen or shorten the arms of the pipe to have both ends stay in the exact center of their respective planes. What I'm getting at is that either way—pipe then planes, or planes then pipe—the size of the one actually, literally, physically determines the size of the other. In this regard the two parts of the work are highly related, highly ordered.

Figs. 15d, 15e:

Schematic illustrations of Donald Judd, untitled, 1962.

Fig. 16:

Donald Judd, untitled (18 Mar 84)

1984. Collage with RAL color samples made for multicolored works, March 18, 1984, 9 7/8 x 13 1/4 inches. Judd Foundation, Marfa, Texas.

So much so that even in the face of their mismatched colors, and shapes, and materials, you can wind up feeling that they're a sort of whole more than they are separate parts. Like how, on balance, the handle of the milk jug is that self-same jug more than it's some different thing stuck on.

The second use of *determine* is when Judd maintains that "this slight linear space [in the pipe] determines the dimensions of the broad [red] planes." That's something else entirely. In claiming it's not the pipe but the space in the pipe which makes the planes the size they are, Judd's going and adding his feelings, his own thought-up relationship and order, to the physical facts. Because if space isn't "true scientifically," and if instead

Fig. 17:

Clyfford Still, untitled

1946. Oil on canvas. Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York. George A. Hearn Fund and Arthur Hoppock Hearn Fund, 1977.

Fig. 18:

Guido Molinari, *Structure jaune-rouge*

1963. Acrylic on canvas. Private collection.

it's "made by thought" and "just the way we feel about it," then these statements should also hold for any amount of determining that space is supposed to do: this too will come down to nothing more than one person's personal thinking and feeling. When all's said and done, however, Judd's belief seems easy enough to follow and maybe even to agree with. Since the pipe determines the sizes of the planes, then, sure, I reckon you might see or feel or think of the space in the pipe as in some sense doing the determining. At any rate, we're talking through several types of space, so far either around or within a single object.

... AND BETWEEN TWO ROCKS

Time for another kind—the space in between two things. We have to go back to the last of the eleven questions that Judd starts us out with. He's trying to keep it basic for beginners yet he still can't come up with any better way to ask which of the two rocks on our sloping plane *joins the plane as an entity*. I'll at least offer a hunch as to what he's suggesting here. Right before, Judd mentions the rock whose top is flat and broader than its sides such that the rock becomes "a thick plane parallel to the surface, level or tilted."⁶⁵ If you see the rock-top and the ground as being "parallel," you may soon find that you're able to look at them as being "join[ed]" in a sense, and after a while possibly even as being one single "entity"—so, increasingly inter-related and integrated the longer you think about them, from mere commonality at first (two planes that simply happen to be parallel), to conformity (joined through their now seemingly mutual paralleling of each other), and finally to unity (in the end not two separate things at all but rather one thing, an entity).

I'll admit it sounds a little strange to speak of added order being there, though perhaps it's not unimaginable. Judd realizes we're bound to have thoughts and feelings about what's out in the world ("about a rock, about anything"), and how such a thought and feeling might well be a sense of order. "Four units in a row are only that," he insists, "a small, finite order that I am interested in," an order which is "mine, someone's, and clearly not some larger order."⁶⁶ "I think that the work is, implies, beyond itself, that it's a relatively chaotic and random world. It just happens to be that I want to order my own particular part of it. So it's not

Fig. 19:
Roger Jorgensen, [title unknown]
1964-65. Acrylic on linen with raised panels. Private collection.

Fig. 20:
Tadasky, B 197
1964. Acrylic on canvas. Private collection.

an overwhelming ordering as you have in the old philosophy, Rationalist philosophy.⁶⁷ We need to keep in mind how the order we see in something is a feeling in us about it—true as far as it goes, but not a property of the object in question, and especially not a hint of or proof of a more universal order at play (because, again, “what you feel and what things are aren’t the same”). Provided we don’t get confused about this fact, however, Judd appears to view it as perfectly natural and even very interesting to carry on thinking our thoughts and feeling our feelings about what’s out in the world.

While we’re on the subject of order we think up and add in certain circumstances, let me spend a minute on Judd’s odd and downright contradictory idea of a *two-color monochrome*. Supposing we have a red spot and a black spot^{fig. 16}

In a way, side by side, the red and the black become one color. They become a two color monochrome. Red and black together are so familiar that they almost form a new unity. Every easily known color paired with either black or white forms such a monochrome: orange, yellow, blue, green. Because of the black and white, also a pair, these pairs have a somewhat flat quality, are somewhat monochromatic.⁶⁸

Certain pairs we take as almost a single color, like black and white. I mean, black and white is so much a pair that you just take it [to be one].... Red and black is, together they’re a very definite pair, they almost make another color.⁶⁹

And there’s more.

The contrasting pairs are just as well known: red and blue, red and green, red and yellow, blue and green, blue and yellow. Some are not: red and orange, yellow and orange. This list is finite, since it is of primaries and secondaries. The other possible pairs are infinite, as is color, whether in the spectrum or materially mixed. All colors of the same value, such as light yellow and light green, make pairs. All values of the same color [like dark green and light green] make pairs.⁷⁰

Judd sees something of the sort in an untitled 1946 painting by Clyfford Still^{fig. 17}. “The relationship of the dark, scumbled brown area to the burnt sienna is characteristic. Still often uses two versions of the same color, approximately two values—light and medium-dark, or that and dark. Sometimes two different colors make a pair of values.”⁷¹ This belief that colors can pair up and turn into a two-color monochrome (which is to say, can be paired up by somebody looking at them and get turned into one) is long-held. At least as far back as 1964 Judd comments on how a couple or more colors side by side look monochromatic. In Guido Molinari’s works, “plain red and yellow together, as in one painting, or those two colors and straight green and blue, as in another piece, are monochromatic, dull in a way. They don’t affect one another very much. They are fairly even”^{fig. 18}.⁷²

In Roger Jorgensen’s paintings, “a black, flat Cubist pattern like the silhouette of a complicated structure has been placed against bright colors, orange in one work. The black and the other dominant color form one kind of monochrome”^{fig. 19}.⁷³ And in a painting by Tadasuke Kuwayama, who to this day goes by Tadasky, “two triads alternate, each bounded by black stripes: red light, blue-green, red light; and red light, cobalt blue, and red light. [Instead of continuing to appear to be two red-blue-red groupings bounded by black,] the red and black become a monochrome, and the two blues become discrete and infrequent”^{fig. 20}.⁷⁴ Ten years later in 1974, it’s Kazimir Malevich’s paintings. “In *Supremus No. 50* the red and black make the most obvious set, a pair in this case, since they are about equal in area.... The larger white ground and the two much smaller yellow squares are also part of the set because all are full color, simple, primary and, in a way, monochromatic when grouped”^{fig. 21}.⁷⁵

Two-color is the physical fact here and *monochrome* is not a physical fact but rather short-hand for order felt by Judd himself. The same goes for “together” and “unity” and “pair”—it’s Judd who views the colors as existing together, he who unifies them, pairs them, makes them one. What accounts for his understanding of added order? With red and black it’s their familiarity, and also proximity. “How far away is the black spot from the red spot?” he asks. “Enough for these to be two discrete spots, one red and one black? Or near enough for there to be a pair of spots, red and black? Or apart enough for this to be uncertain?”⁷⁶ With these two colors you find certain qualities giving rise to a feeling of order.

Now back to space. “If two objects are close together they define the space in between,” Judd states squarely.⁷⁷ Instead of two spots, let’s say you come across two rocks. Of course the rocks, the distance that separates them, and the rest of the physical facts of the situation at hand remain unchanged whether you’re thinking about them or not. Yet as with the red and black spots, the nearness of the two rocks makes you inclined to see

Fig. 21:
Kazimir Malevich, *Supremus No. 50*
1915. Oil on canvas. Stedelijk Museum, Amsterdam.

order—a pair of rocks—and the feeling of a greater degree of order, over and above the very little or none at all there to begin with, defines the undefined openness from this rock to the other and turns it into a space between.

Whether the rocks are close or far surely is an important consideration, although other qualities like their size also affect the order and the space. Judd: “two rocks of equal size and the space between them is a situation which is very different from that of a small rock and a large rock with the same space between.”⁷⁸ He takes this as obvious and doesn’t bother to spell out how and why the situations are so unlike. That’s okay I guess, and in light of his circumstances at the time of writing I hate to keep on about it, but there’s a problem here. The words aren’t quite right. When he says *same space between*, Judd slips back into the ordinary use of *space* to mean only how far two things are from each other. What he’s aiming to get across here is that while the like- and unlike-sized pairs have the same distance between rocks, they’ll nevertheless bring to mind two pretty distinct spaces. Fine, but again, how, why? Well, two rocks of similar size near one another make me think of my morning medicine capsule or a bull-snake egg full of space, with a rock inside at either end. And a small rock and a large rock exactly as far apart make me think of an ice-cream cone of space, sort of a lop-sided tear-drop that starts big and broad and tapers down to a tight knob. Then there’re more qualities of the rocks to go over, like shape, and color, and mineral make-up, on and on. Any can be factors in how the rocks carry on with defining a space for you.

Or in how they don’t. “These definitions are infinite until the two objects are so far apart that the distance in between is no longer space.”⁷⁹ The farther two rocks get from each other, the less likely you are to see them as a pair—and when order breaks down, the space between does too. Naturally such a lack of order, and therefore space, can come about for

Fig. 22:
Donald Judd, untitled
1985. Enameled aluminum.
Private collection.

Fig. 23:
Donald Judd, installation view
Donald Judd: The Multicolored Works, Pulitzer Foundation for the Arts, St. Louis,
May 10, 2013 to January 4, 2014.

plenty of reasons. Two lone rocks only a few feet apart in a barren clearing might be a pair and form a space, yet those same rocks at that same distance might not do so in the middle of a stand of trees or thick underbrush or what have you. Likewise you may not view a boulder and a pebble as a sensible pairing, or two rocks whose shapes are entirely at odds, or any two particular rocks of the many in a rocky outcropping.

“Then the passerby remembers that one was there and another here.”⁸⁰ All of a sudden the emptiness separating the two rocks is shot through with order and it becomes a space. “The space between can even be more definite than the two objects which establish it; it can be a single space more than the two objects are a pair.”⁸¹ A pointy gray boulder perched on a hill-side and, some ways off, a rounded brown pebble resting on the flat-lands—I believe you’ll be hard put to see these rocks as a pair, though it might just be possible if you find nothing much else of note in the void you walk through from one to the other. And, according to Judd, the weak order shared by the two thoroughly unlike rocks can still create a clear-cut space in such wide-open surroundings. With these two rocks you find certain qualities giving rise to a feeling of order, and order giving rise to a space between.

From rocks to order, and from order to space. It’s by thinking, by feeling, that Judd or you or I or anybody brings on this transformation. So at last back to question number eleven about our rocks. Again, the sentence goes, “if they are on a slope, which is higher, which joins the plane as an entity?” As written, the two phrases *which is higher* and *which joins the plane as an entity* might be in opposition (that is, the second contrasting with the first, as in, *If they are on a slope, which is higher, which is lower?*), or they may be equivalent (with the second restating the first, *If they are on a slope, which is higher, which is closer to the top?*). That said, I read the two as altogether separate questions which Judd places next to each other in a single sentence because he himself thinks and feels there’s a relationship between being higher and joining the plane, so, not an opposition but not really a true equivalence either. You and I needn’t necessarily agree with him, however.

Which rock would you say is higher? Well *higher* isn’t made by you thinking or feeling, higher is just higher. You report the physical fact in front of your eyes as best you can. Then, which rock joins the plane as an entity? Here it depends. It hinges on which rock or rocks—the higher, the lower, both, or neither—you yourself *make* join the plane by seeing order there between them, between the rock or rocks and the plane. After you figure this much out, kindly tell us if as a result you start to notice any space between the rocks. For Judd it might be something along the lines of the thick plane he refers to before, a slab of space that keeps low to the ground while following its slope from the higher rock to the lower. Hard to know for sure. And anyway the order and the space you fix on will stray from what he comes up with, since you’re now the one doing the thinking and the feeling that make them.

* * *

Fig. 24:
Schematic illustration of fig. 23.

How about non-rock examples. You can view first-hand the space around and inside and between what they call Judd's multi-color works, which really show off some of the things you can do with color, order, and space—especially when they're in a single small room.⁸² What seems to me to come about is just the sort of tutorial Judd might be calling for, some practice that gets us up to speed, at last, on not only the basics but also some fairly advanced ideas about space. Things such as: how you and I make it, how an art object gets us to make it, what types or degrees it or we make, and how when it doesn't get made, why not.

If you ask me, a half-apple of space appears to be surrounding the work on the south wall of the little room in question, as if the art were a rock sitting in a field that's been turned upright^{fig. 22}. The three and a half feet below the thing is well-defined down to the floor. But instead of fitting

its wall to a T, the apple falls short of reaching the ceiling and side-walls that are farther off than the floor is. This is interesting to test out in person: a point three feet away from the object in any direction is related to it, defined by it, and within its spatial apple. Go another full foot, though, and in places the order and definition and space begin to come undone or already don't exist anymore.

Then, unlike a rock yet like a jar, this work of Judd's also creates space on its insides, actually two kinds. For starters, each of the empty pans wraps part-way round its own brick of space. And when bolted one to the next, the pans and their bricks wrap round the void running through the middle of the larger pipe-like assembly that they form all together. The colored metal means the contours of the emptiness within both the single pans and the overall object are sharply visible and physical. That in turn defines the two sorts of openness, and helps make each into a space.

Now as for space between two things, we're aware of how it relies on your feeling of out-of-the-ordinary order between them. With these multi-color works, the more-than-usual degree can follow from the shared shape, close-by positioning, and matching colors, like it does with Judd's spots and rocks. So, with this one on the wall, the red, orange, black, and white result in six monochromatic pairings: red-orange, red-black, red-white, orange-black, orange-white, black-white. ("The relationships of the colors are differently intelligible," however, Judd notes. "One above another they are easy to see as a pair; diagonally they are not."⁸³) Another object on the west wall of the same room also happens to end with orange and black pans^{fig. 23}. Together, a set here and a set there, the two orange-and-black pairs pair up on the strength of being the self-same two-color monochrome. And from that straight-forward instance of order—two alike things only a little ways apart with nothing much else in between—comes thoughts and feelings of a space, maybe a right-angled bar stretching out of both works into and around the corner of the room^{fig. 24}. There's

Fig. 25:
Donald Judd, installation view
Donald Judd: The Multicolored Works, Pulitzer Foundation for the Arts, St. Louis,
May 10, 2013 to January 4, 2014.

orange-and-black yet again in a third object on the north wall^{fig. 25}. This time, though, the pairing is part of the work's own ABCABC sequence, and, for me, that internal order outweighs the likeness to the orange-and-black in the other two objects. That means no space really takes hold between it and either of them. Last, predictably, I don't notice much of a space between any of the three works and a fourth on the east wall without orange-and-black.

But, as before, there are grounds besides shared color for seeing a greater degree of order and then a defined space. Align a couple or more of these things, and they tend to want to make a space from one to the other to the next, regardless of color. For that matter, a row of parts in any single object by Judd will create space, like what's in between the units progressing sideways in the so-called progressions, and the units stacked up-and-down in the so-called stacks, and the four big units in *To Susan Buckwalter* (again, ^{fig. 12}). Somebody in the audience at a talk of Judd's mentions how "the space between the cubes is very dense."⁸⁴ He replies, "the space between the units, the boxes, or whatever they are, is very important of course.... If you make it too far apart, it becomes just [undefined] space between the boxes, so you've got to make some equivalence between the volume of the boxes or the enclosed space [within the boxes,] and the open space [between the boxes]."

This discussion about the space between things soon leads to looking harder at walls, floors, and ceilings—to architecture, and how to "make a room."⁸⁵ (Assuming we get ourselves caught up, that is: "Of course I can't continue, I can't mention what would happen if a stick were put across the two stones."⁸⁶ All the more reason why it's important for us to try and do so.) "The room is a general space; it's not very particular in its quality," and "if you have a bad architectural situation, you can destroy the space, or destroy the space, or harm the space anyway, that the ah piece itself makes."⁸⁷ It's in the early '70s when Judd says, "I got a little tired of big pieces that just sit there in an indefinite space, so I wanted to do something that deals more with the space of the room."⁸⁸ "Like that wall

Fig. 27:
Las Casas, Ayala de Chinati ranch
Presidio County, Texas.

Fig. 26:
Donald Judd, untitled
1970. Hot-dipped galvanized iron. Installation view, Castelli Gallery, 1970.

that went around Leo's front room [Leo Castelli Gallery, ⁶⁹⁻²⁶]—it was an attempt to deal with, with the whole space and make it clear, ah rather than let the space generated by the object just sort of trail off in four directions."⁸⁹ In '81 Judd comes right out with the big idea. "What is needed is a created space, space made by someone, space that is formed as is a solid, the two the same, with the space and the solid defining each other."⁹⁰ And then in '93, in what he has to sense is going to be some of his last writing, Judd takes it on himself to piece together the beginnings of a history of his objects that make space in a room, and also to plainly state his discovery.

I found that if I placed a work on a wall or on the ground, I wondered where it was. I found that if I placed a work on a wall in relation to a corner or to both corners, or similarly on the floor, or outdoors near a change in the surface of the ground, that by adjusting the distance the space in between became much more clear than before, definite, like the work. If the space in one or two directions can become clear, it's logical to desire the space in all directions to become clear.⁹¹

In the end the point is this, that when you look at a work of art by Donald Judd you've got to see if you see the space he's aiming to make clear—that which is around the thing, and within it, and between it and whatever else.

* * *

On a hill at Judd's ranch, Las Casas he calls it, in Presidio County, Texas, you'll come upon an oddly-small iron-railed corral (again, ⁶⁹⁻⁹). Turns out it's the burial site of Mr. Filiberto Guerrero, 1911–1987, may he rest in peace, and it creates space around, inside, above, and below. As does another grave alongside ⁶⁹⁻²⁷. This one is unmarked, a soft-cornered rectangle of hard-edged rocks It makes a column six feet down, but also up and then off into the sky.

The art exists. That's not metaphysical. There's the art and something exists, and other people later figure it out as best they can. They're not going to understand all of it, either.⁹²

The knowledge of space which I've made grew swiftly. This is a great deal of knowledge, but not written, knowledge of a peculiar kind as visual art, made by a person, sometimes intelligible to other persons, not made by snakes or owls, probably not intelligible to intelligent beings elsewhere, perhaps not to our descendants in ten thousand years. The work is a great deal of knowledge about space, which is necessarily related to the space of architecture. This knowledge is, to me, particular and plentifully diverse; to almost everyone it doesn't exist; it's invisible.⁹³

installations. Several years later Yayoi Kusama made a free-standing room and Lucas Samaras also. In 1967 in Los Angeles a work of Carl Andre's, *8 Cuts*, covered the floor of the gallery."

9 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 7, lines re-ordered.

10 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 5, 11.

11 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11.

12 "I gather that [since] most people don't understand it, that my work needs a defense." Donald Judd, Baldwin Seminar talk, Oberlin College, February 26, 1976, audio recording, Oberlin College Archives, Oberlin, Ohio, part 1, at 4:05.

13 Judd takes issue with how Piet Mondrian, Kazimir Malevich, and Theo van Doesburg get disparaged for being idealistic and utopian, and it sounds like a justification of his own efforts too. "Why is it idealistic—even what does that mean—to want to do something new and beneficial, practical also, in a new civilization? Is it practical to let the civilization become as gross as it is becoming, to let it become stagnant, and then in a few hundred years try to aerate it? By then it will be completely inert, so that nothing can be done and nothing even imagined to be done. No one will realize that there isn't a civilization. As usual the civilization will be convinced of not being one by its collapse." Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 19–20.

14 On Panza, you can read Donald Judd, "Una Stanza per Panza," parts 1–4, *Kunst Intern* 4 (May 1990), 3–14; *Kunst Intern* 5 (July 1990), 3–14; *Kunst Intern* 6 (September 1990), 3–12; *Kunst Intern* 7 (November 1990), 3–22. There're also the entries for April 1970, Autumn 1973, April 1976, May 1980, September 1988, November 1989, and May 1990 in Kopie's timeline (note 4), 255–67. On Saatchi, read Judd, "Una Stanza per Panza," part 4, page 3, and the entry for September 1981 in Kopie's timeline (note 4), 260. On the "sixty-four mistakes" in the booklet for *Don Judd*, May 11–July 4, 1971, at the Pasadena Art Museum, read Donald Judd, "Complaints, Part II," *Arts Magazine* 47, no. 5 (March 1973), 31; and "Errata and Addenda," slipped-in page included with *Don Judd* (Pasadena: Pasadena Art Museum, 1971).

15 "The narrow and lazy nature of art criticism makes it difficult to know the diversity of my work, or of anyone's." "Art historians of the past are at least interested in chronology. Art historians of the present are not. It's too real and interferes with treating the present as the past, but with less substance, a subject of their speculation." Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 12, 22.

16 "One work occupying a whole room is still alive and new in the work of a few artists—Roni Horn, Michael Schulz, Ilya Kabakov—but many artists degrade the idea, for example Barbara Kruger, who is my favorite, because she also degrades red and black." Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11–12.

17 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 7. James Boswell, *The Life of Samuel Johnson, LL.D.*, 2 vols. (London: Charles Dilly, 1791), 1:257, emphasis as in the original: "After we came out of the church, we stood talking for some time together of Bishop Berkeley's ingenious sophistry to prove the non-existence of matter, and that every thing in the universe is merely ideal. I observed, that though we are satisfied his doctrine is not true, it is impossible to refute it. I never shall forget the alacrity with which Johnson answered, striking his foot with mighty force against a large stone, till he rebounded from it, 'I refute it thus.'" And below is Wallace Stevens, "Anecdote of the Jar," *Poetry, A Magazine of Verse* 15, no. 1 (October 1919), 8:

Anecdote of the Jar

I placed a jar in Tennessee,
And round it was, upon a hill.
It made the slovenly wilderness
Surround that hill.

The wilderness rose up to it,
And sprawled around, no longer wild.
The jar was round upon the ground
And tall and of a port in air.

It took dominion everywhere.
The jar was gray and bare.
It did not give of bird or bush,
Like nothing else in Tennessee.

18 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 19, 26.

19 Donald Judd, "21 February 93," *Donald Judd: Large-Scale Works* (New York: The Pace Gallery, 1993), 13.

For their kind help I'm much obliged to David Batchelor, Marisa Bourgoïn, Liz Coffey, Arcy Douglass, Adam Free, Tara Hart, Gary Hespeneide, Nancy Teufel Jorgensen, Flavin Judd, Rainer Judd, Patricia Kuwayama, Jana LaBrasca, Klaus Stefan Leuschel, Jessica McIntyre, Randy Miyake, Caitlin Murray, Ian North, David Platzker, Carl E. Ryan, Randy Sanchez, Craig Schiffer, Ruth Elena Stifter-Trummer, Marianne Stockebrand, Jenna Stout, David Tompkins, Rob Weiner, Emma Whelan, Jin Whittington, Ryan P. Young, and Guillermo Zuaznabar.

Shortened citations of sources in the notes below include a reference in parentheses to the note with the first and full citation.

1 Donald Judd, "Yale Lecture, September 20, 1983," *Res: Anthropology and Aesthetics* 7/8 (Spring/Autumn 1984), 150.

2 Donald Judd, "A Long Discussion Not About Master-pieces but Why There Are So Few of Them, Part II," *Art in America* 72, no. 9 (October 1984), 10.

3 Donald Judd, interview with Joshua Homnick and daughter Rainer Judd, Porter House, Marfa, Texas, October 10, 1993, video recording, Judd Foundation Archives, Marfa, Texas, at 7:55. Homnick (at 7:32): "And so, I don't know if you've made up your mind yet, oops, about it, or, I mean, in in ah, for you personally I'd really be interested to know, they don't, how do you believe, like, metaphysically, do you be—, wh-what will happen to you personally along with your consciousness?"

4 Donald Judd, interview with Marfa students and teacher May Quick, undated video recording labeled "Walking Tour Dia / Dia Foundation Archives," Chinati Foundation Archives, Marfa, Texas, at 3:12. In November 1971 Judd rents a house and building in Marfa; he buys during 1973 and 1974; and in 1977 he starts living most of the year in Texas. This, according to entries in Jeffrey Kopie's timeline of Judd's life in *Donald Judd*, ed. Nicholas Serota (London: Tate, 2004), 256–58.

5 Marianne Stockebrand, email, February 7, 2013; and entries for 1993 and 1994 in Kopie's timeline (note 4), 270. There're also several writings by Tim Martin, like "Donald Judd: The Cathexis of Space," (*a*): *A Journal of Culture and the Unconscious* 6, no. 1 (2006), 68–69; "Judd's Badge," in *Sculpture and Psychoanalysis*, ed. Brandon Taylor (Aldershot: Ashgate Publishing Limited, 2006), 62, 64; and "Donald Judd: Architecture and Φ Space," *Haecceity Papers* 4, no. 1 (Fall 2008), 34–35. Judd dies on the twelfth of February, 1994.

6 Donald Judd, *Some Aspects of Color in General and Red and Black in Particular* (Sassenheim: Sikkens Foundation, 1993), 7, 11, 12, 22, 25, lines re-ordered.

7 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11.

8 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11. More: "Oldenburg's Store was a store but it could be called an installation. Bob Whitman's performances occurred in

20 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 5–6, 13, lines re-ordered.

21 Judd, “Yale Lecture” (note 1), 150; Donald Judd, interview with Catherine Millet, Galerie Maeght Le-long, Paris, April 1987, transcript translated by Pascale Haas and published as “La petite logique de Donald Judd,” *Art Press* 119 (November 1987), 9 (the line in French is, “L’étendue du temps par rapport à la vie qui est très courte est tout à fait évidente”); Donald Judd, interview with Jochen Poetter, Staatliche Kunsthalle Baden-Baden, August 7, 1989, transcript published as “Back to Clarity: Interview with Donald Judd,” *Donald Judd* (Baden-Baden: Staatliche Kunsthalle Baden-Baden, 1989), 90, and Donald Judd, a note from March 12, 1989, in *Donald Judd Writings*, ed. Flavin Judd and Caitlin Murray (New York: Judd Foundation, 2016), 524; Donald Judd, “Monument to the Last Horse: Animo et Fide,” in Claes Oldenburg and Coosje van Bruggen, *Large-Scale Projects* (New York: The Monacelli Press, 1994), 484 (on 477 it says this text by Judd is from 1993; but according to *Donald Judd Writings*, 790, it’s 1992); and Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 22.

22 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

23 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6, lines re-arranged into a numbered list.

24 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

25 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9.

26 D[onald] J[udd], “Alberto Giacometti,” *Arts Magazine* 36, no. 5 (February 1962), 42. Judd mentions “Giacometti’s device of establishing the core of a space” in his review of Fritz Koenig as well. D[onald] J[udd], “Fritz Koenig,” *Arts* 35, no. 5 (February 1961), 53.

27 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9.

28 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9.

29 “Interview: Kasper König and Donald Judd,” *Donald Judd* (Botrop: Moderne Galerie Botrop, 1977), 7. The published German text reads, “Schen Sie, ich bin ein Raum interessiert und ein dem, was den Raum definiert, an dem, was sichtbar ist.” But an English transcript with Judd’s handwritten edits has something different, “You see I am interested in space and what can be seen.” “Gespräch mit D. Judd,” English transcripts, Kasper König Papers, Zentralarchiv für deutsche und internationale Kunstmarktforschung, Cologne, item G20, IX, 2, page 14, part 2.

30 Donald Judd, interview, Marfa, Texas, June 3, 1992, video recording in *Donald Judd’s Marfa Texas*, dir. Chris Felver, 1998, at 20:44. Judd takes care to point out how “philosophically, it’s probably very dangerous to say that time and space don’t exist,” before going right on ahead and supporting this position. “They’re made by something happening in them, in the case of time, or by something existing in them, in the case of space” (at 20:32 and 21:01). About time and space being made and not existing otherwise, you can also read Donald Judd, a note from January 3, 1976, in *Donald Judd Writings* (note 21), 283; Donald Judd, statement in “Two Contemporary Artists Comment,” *Art Journal* 41, no. 3 (Fall 1981), 250; Judd, “Yale Lecture” (note 1), 153; Donald Judd, interview with Klaus Stefan Leuschel, Eichholterren, Küssnacht am Rigi, April 22, 1992, audio recording, Judd Foundation Archives, Marfa, Texas, tape 1, side 2, at 7:31; Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9; and Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

31 Donald Judd, in “The New Sculpture: A Symposium on Primary Structures,” *The Jewish Museum*, New York, May 2, 1966, edited transcript, box 2, folder 5, Barbara Rose Papers, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., 13.

32 Donald Judd, interview with Angeli Janhsen and others, Ruhr-Universität, Bochum, February 1, 1990, transcript published as “Discussion with Donald Judd,” *Donald Judd* (St. Gallen: Kunstverein St. Gallen, 1990), 55; and *Donald Judd’s Marfa Texas* (note 30), at 19:19.

33 Donald Judd, interview with Katharina Winnekes, Cologne, December 14, 1992, transcript published as “Interview with Donald Judd,” *Kunst und Kirche*, no. 2/93 (April 1993), 136.

34 *Donald Judd’s Marfa Texas* (note 30), at 21:16; and Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6. In one of his college notebooks Judd copies a sentence from Alfred Edward Taylor’s *Elements of Metaphysics* (1903; London: Methuen and Co., Ltd., 1912), 245: “The space + time system of each individual’s perception is composed of directions radiating out from his unique here and now, + is . . . [and is therefore] individual to himself.” Sheets labeled “Space + Time,” box 2, folder 6, Donald Judd

University Papers, Judd Foundation Archives, Marfa, Texas, back of page 1.

35 Don Judd, “Jackson Pollock,” *Arts Magazine* 41, no. 6 (April 1967), 34; and Donald Judd, “A Long Discussion Not About Master-pieces but Why There Are So Few of Them, Part I,” *Art in America* 72, no. 8 (September 1984), 13. It’s after Gian Lorenzo Bernini, says Judd, “that the belief slowly dies in the direct correspondence of one’s feelings about the external world with the real nature of that world. The artist can no longer look at the world, put it in a picture, and claim reality, a similar reality, for both acts. More and more the portrayal of the natural world is as the artist feels it, not as it is.” Donald Judd, “Abstract Expressionism” (1983), in *Complete Writings, 1975–1986* (Eindhoven: Van Abbemuseum, 1987), 38.

36 Judd, “Monument to the Last Horse” (note 21), 481; and D[onald] J[udd], “Walter Murch,” *Arts Magazine* 37, no. 5 (February 1963), 46.

37 Donald Judd, video recording of interview in *Bilderstreit: Europa gegen die Vereinigten Staaten?*, dir. Rainer Ostendorf, 1989, at 8:14. There’s also Donald Judd, interview with Lucy R. Lippard, New York, April 10, 1968, audio recording, box 36, folder 40, Lucy R. Lippard Papers, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., reel 2, at 1:29:02; and Richard Schiff, “Judd Through Oldenburg,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 9 (October 2004), 33–44.

38 D[onald] J[udd], “Jean Arp,” *Arts Magazine* 37, no. 10 (September 1963), 54. The original version of Judd’s review doesn’t have a picture of Arp’s art, but two reprints of it include an image of an object titled *Sculpture Classique* that plainly represents a figure. For this reason it’s a bad example of the “emptiness” Judd praises. “The least likable sculptures are the few which actually resemble the human body. *Sculpture Classique* is obviously a standing figure, although smoothed and without feet. *Demeter* is also insufficiently changed.” To get the point he’s making, you need to be looking at one with only an “oblique reference” to the body, like *Croissance*. (Further confusing the matter is how the *Sculpture Classique* in the show Judd is reviewing—April 29–May 25, 1963, at Sidney Janis Gallery—is listed in the exhibition booklet as a 1960 bronze, while both reprints of Judd’s review have images of a marble sculpture, one dated 1960 and the other 1964.) *Exhibition of Sculpture by Jean Arp in Marble, Bronze and Wood Relief from the Years: 1923–63* (New York: Sidney Janis Gallery, 1963), nos. 1, 25, and 26; Donald Judd, “Jean Arp” (1963), *Complete Writings, 1959–1975* (Halifax: The Press of the Nova Scotia College of Art and Design, 1975), 92; and “Judd on Arp,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 17 (October 2012), 58–59. For more, you can also read Arie Hartog, “Looking at Arp (Reading Judd),” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 17 (October 2012), 54–56.

39 Judd, “Monument to the Last Horse” (note 21), 481.

40 Donald Judd, “3 December 86,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 20 (October 2015), back cover.

41 Donald Judd, talk titled “Abstract Expressionism,” video recording, The Open University / British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) Television, 1983, at 8:14.

42 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9.

43 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 55.

44 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 55.

45 *Donald Judd’s Marfa Texas* (note 30), at 21:31.

46 Donald Judd, talk at the Musée National d’Art Moderne, Paris, May 22, 1987, audio recording, box 183, folder 10, Leo Castelli Gallery Records, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., side B, at 21:24.

47 Donald Judd, interview with Friedrich Teja Bach, May 5, 1975, corrected transcript, Judd Foundation Archives, Marfa, Texas, unnumbered first page.

48 Donald Judd, interview with Barbara Rose, 101 Spring Street, New York, 1972, in a re-recording of the “Don Judd Interview” audio reel for the film *American Art in the 1960s*, dir. Michael Blackwood, 1972, Michael Blackwood Collection, Harvard Film Archive, Cambridge, Massachusetts, at 29:24 and 29:06, phrases re-ordered.

49 Judd, talk at the Musée National d’Art Moderne (note 46), side B, at 22:06. On space in the concrete objects and also in the rest of Judd’s art, there’re the edited transcripts of 2009 lectures by James Lawrence and Richard Schiff published in “On Donald Judd’s Concrete Works,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 15 (October 2010), 6–17 and 18–25.

50 D[onald] J[udd], “Robert Morris,” *Arts Magazine* 39, no. 5 (February 1965), 54.

51 Judd, interview with Marfa students (note 4), at 6:20. I can’t tell for sure which work she has in mind, but judging from the video recording from about 5:13 to 9:37, it appears to be *To Susan Buckwalter* of 1964. “Susan Buckwalter was a collector of contemporary art from Kansas City, Missouri. This object was dedicated to her when Judd learned of her death in January 1965.” Dudley Del Balso, Roberta Smith, and Brydon Smith, “Catalogue Raisonné of Paintings, Objects, and Wood-Blocks, 1960–1974,” in Brydon Smith, *Donald Judd* (Ottawa: The National Gallery of Canada, 1975), 122, no. 56.

52 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9. And, again, note 17 for Samuel Johnson and Wallace Stevens.

53 Donald Judd, interview with Margot Willett, May 1968, audio recording, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution, Washington, D.C., at 18:09 and 18:29.

54 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 9, 10, lines re-ordered.

55 Donald Judd, video recording of interview in *Kulturjournal: Judd*, Österreichischer Rundfunk (ORF), air date March 10, 1988, ORF Multimediales Archiv, Vienna, at 0:44.

56 Donald Judd, “Chamberlain: Another View,” *Art International* 7, no. 10 (January 16, 1964 / Christmas–New Year, 1963–64), 39.

57 “Don Judd: An Interview with John Coplans,” *Don Judd* (Pasadena: Pasadena Art Museum, 1971), 44; John Coplans, “An Interview with Don Judd,” *Artforum* 9, no. 10 (June 1971), 50; and Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 10. The work is listed as “destroyed” in Del Balso, Smith, and Smith, “Catalogue Raisonné” (note 51), 169, no. 129.

58 David Raskin, “Specific Opposition: Judd’s Art and Politics,” *Art History* 24, no. 5 (November 2001), 688–90; Richard Schiff, “A Space of One to One,” *Donald Judd: 50 x 100 x 50, 100 x 100 x 50* (New York: PaceWildenstein, 2002), 10–11; Carina Plath, “Donald Judd: The Early Work, 1955–1968,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 7 (October 2002), 13; Martin, “Donald Judd: The Cathexis of Space” (note 5), 67–69, 73–74; Martin, “Judd’s Badge” (note 5), 64; Martin, “Donald Judd: Architecture and Φ Space” (note 5), 26–30, 35; Marianne Stockebrand, “The Whole Judd,” *Chinati Foundation Newsletter* 17 (October 2012), 6; and Gail Hastings, “The Power of Inclusion in Donald Judd’s Art: Observations by an Artist,” *Art Journal* 77, no. 3 (Fall 2018), 48–62.

59 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11. When he says *black as space*, I think Judd means how you see a few inches down into the open hole of the pipe as you look at either of the outer sides of the work. The blackness there, an actual lack of light reflecting back to your eye, is darker than and otherwise different from the coat of black paint on the pipe that is always going to reflect some light even as it absorbs most. So you have three colors here: cadmium red light oil paint on the wood, black enamel on the pipe, and the black of an unlit hole—“red and black, and black as space.”

60 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 11. I believe I’m keeping these lines how Judd intends them, but one phrase can go three different ways and change the entire description. When he refers to *space within the angle*, he may have in mind either what’s inside the overall red angle (which is how I’m reading it), or what’s inside the black pipe angle (in other words, the shaft of space that runs up the inner corner and is bordered by the pipe and the red boards), or, again, what’s inside the black pipe angle (though now meaning where water would be). These are the third, the fourth, and the fifth type of space, respectively, that I’ll get to in just a minute.

61 Donald Judd, interview with Ian North, Art Gallery of South Australia, Adelaide, May 30, 1974, audio recording, Art Gallery of South Australia Archives, track 2, at 4:05.

62 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 55.

63 Carl Ryan, video recording of interview in *Marfa Voices*, dir. Karen Bernstein and Rainer Judd, 2010, at 14:23: “I remember one time, Billy Shurley, who was Jane Shurley’s husband and a rancher, ah walking through the field and looking at the concrete pieces, and talking about ‘negative space.’ Here was a rancher in Presidio County, who hadn’t thought for the first

few years of his life about anything other than Western Art, and now he’s talking about negative space.”

64 According to Judd this is in fact what happens. “The bent and welded pipe was found.... The construction and dimension are a function of the pipe.... The asymmetrical disposition is determined by the pipe, which I found that way, so that the pipe is a given thing. . . . I think you realize that the pipe has determined the shape of the piece.” “Don Judd: An Interview with John Coplans” (note 57), 23; and Coplans, “An Interview with Don Judd,” (note 57), 41, 43.

65 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

66 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 25; and Don Judd, statement in “Portfolio: 4 Sculptors,” *Perspecta* 11 (1967), 44. There’s also David Raskin, *Donald Judd* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 2010), 2, 126 n. 6, and throughout.

67 Donald Judd, interview with Michael Archer, Waddington Galleries, London, March 1986, audio recording in *Audio Arts* 8, nos. 2 and 3 (1987), tape 2, side 2, at 19:26, Tate Archive, London.

68 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 28.

69 Judd, interview with Archer (note 67), at 15:03 and 15:30.

70 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 28.

71 Judd, “Abstract Expressionism” (note 41), at 13:00.

72 D[onald] J[udd], “Guido Molinari,” *Arts Magazine* 38, no. 6 (March 1964), 68.

73 D[onald] J[udd], “Roger Jorgensen,” *Arts Magazine* 38, no. 7 (April 1964), 37. The work shown here seems something like the one Judd’s describing, but it’s yellow and dark blue not orange and black.

74 D[onald] J[udd], “Tadasky,” *Arts Magazine* 39, no. 5 (February 1965), 63. Again, this painting is the closest I can find based on the colors Judd lists, though it has only a single type of blue, not two.

75 Donald Judd, “Malevich: Independent Form, Color, Surface,” *Art in America* 62, no. 2 (March–April 1974), 56.

76 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 28.

77 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

78 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

79 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6.

80 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 6–7.

81 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 7.

82 It’s one room of *Donald Judd: The Multicolored Works*, curated by Marianne Stockebrand, at the Pulitzer Foundation for the Arts in St. Louis from May 10, 2013 to January 4, 2014.

83 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 31.

84 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 52.

85 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 56. And Donald Judd, in the 7 for 67 symposium, City Art Museum of St. Louis, October 1, 1967, transcript, Richardson Memorial Library and Museum Archives, Saint Louis Art Museum, page 5: The artworks “need a good deal of space around them. Sometimes they have to do with a particular dimension of a room, something they don’t. And they could have even more to do with a particular dimension of a room. But again that get’s into something more ambitious, making your own room and so forth.”

86 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 7.

87 Janhsen, “Discussion with Donald Judd” (note 32), 55; and Donald Judd, interview with Francesco Poli, Turin, 1988, video recording in *Donald Judd at the Castello di Rivoli*, dir. Gianfranco Barberi and Marco di Castri, 1988, Whitney Museum of American Art Archives, New York, at 12:49.

88 “Don Judd: An Interview with John Coplans” (note 57), 44; and Coplans, “An Interview with Don Judd,” (note 57), 50.

89 Judd, interview with Rose (note 48), at 29:13. And Beth Fagan, “Plain Old Art” Creates New Space in Environment of pcVA,” *The Oregonian*, November 10, 1974, B15: “Judd said he is still doing free-standing pieces that deal with immediate space around them, ‘shading off into general space,’ but that he’s now trying to deal with space in a more complete way.”

90 Judd, statement in “Two Contemporary Artists Comment” (note 30), 250.

91 Judd, “21 February 93” (note 19), 10.

92 Judd, interview with Homnick and Rainer Judd (note 3), at 8:34.

93 Judd, *Some Aspects of Color* (note 6), 8.